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THE LEAGUE OF NATIONS AND THE UNITED NATIONS: PROBLEMS AND LESSONS

Abstract:

Based on the collected materials, successes and failures in the activities of the League of Nations and the United Nations (UN) were analyzed. These institutions were created to prevent wars and promote international peace and security.

The League of Nations successfully resolved a number of international conflicts and disputes in the 1920s, such as the Åland Crisis and the Greco-Bulgarian conflict. The UN has played a key role in promoting human rights and conducting peacekeeping missions.

The League of Nations failed to prevent aggression by Japan, Italy, and Germany, leading to World War II. The UN is currently criticized for its ineffectiveness and insufficient response to crises such as the war in Syria and Ukraine. The need to reform the UN in connection with new challenges to global security is emphasized.

Key words: *League of Nations, UN, Cold War, Security Council, right of veto.*

The war in Ukraine, the Israeli-Palestinian conflict, and tensions in the Pacific region are serious challenges for international organizations, primarily the UN. Studying the problems of international law, the experience of peacekeeping operations, the factors of success and failure of international organizations remains relevant even at today's stage of Ukraine's development. In the conditions of globalization of political and economic life, the significance of intergovernmental organizations as a tool of international cooperation is increasing. Studying and accounting for success factors can help in finding ways to reform the UN, which in turn will help restore peace in the regions.

Russian aggression against Ukraine demonstrated strong international support for our country, particularly from the UN. However, the situation shows that the measures of international organizations and military-political blocs are insufficient to deter the aggressor. Parallels between the current situation and the events of the 20s and 30s of the 20th century draw the attention of researchers to the role of international organizations - the League of Nations and the UN. There is an array of literature devoted to international law and international organizations (for example, the works of T. Drachova, K. Lisogorova), as well as separate studies of the activities of the League of Nations (S. Vidnyansky, K. Kolesnichenko) and the UN (T. Grachevska, A. Girman, Ya. Zhukorska, I. Patlashynska, A. Skrypnyk).

The article provides examples of the activities of these organizations in relation to the settlement of international conflicts. The analysis of these examples shows that both institutions as guarantors of international peace and mediators in the resolution of disputes had both achievements and failures in the implementation of their mission.

In the history of the emergence of both organizations, we can trace noticeable similarities. World wars were the catalyst for the creation of both security organizations.

The First World War (1914-1918) claimed the lives of millions of soldiers and civilians. The victorious countries sought to create an international organization to prevent new conflicts. The initiator of this idea was US President Woodrow Wilson. His famous the Fourteen Points, put forward in 1918, included the idea of creating a League of Nations as one of the key instruments of world order. He formulated the goal of the future unification as "creating a mutual guarantee of political independence and territorial integrity of both large and small states" [9, p. 7]. The League of Nations was supposed to adjudicate disputes between member states to protect their sovereignty and territorial rights. In case of aggression, the League could introduce economic sanctions, for example, the cessation of trade.

The League of Nations was founded in 1920 and included 42 countries. In its heyday (1934-1935), the League included 58 states covering almost the entire world, including most of Southeast Asia, Europe, and South America. However, the United States did not join the League of Nations because the Senate, which followed a largely isolationist policy, refused to ratify the League's constitution [9, p.7].

The League of Nations had positive cases of resolving interstate disputes. We can include the conflict between Sweden and Finland over the Åland Islands. After reviewing the situation in 1921, the League decided that the islands should be part of Finland, but with broad autonomy. Thus, a potential war between the two countries was avoided [4, p.42]. In 1925, there was an incident between border guards on the border between Greece and Bulgaria. In response, the Greek army invaded the territory of Bulgaria. Bulgaria, trusting the

League of Nations to settle the dispute, ordered its troops to offer only symbolic resistance. The League condemned the invasion of Greece and demanded the withdrawal of Greek troops and the payment of compensation to Bulgaria. Greece was forced to give way [4, p.42].

The League of Nations was also successful outside of Europe. In 1932, territorial disputes between Colombia and Peru turned into an armed conflict. Both states agreed to the mediation of the League of Nations. A temporary peace agreement placed the disputed territory under the control of the League pending negotiations. In 1934, the final peace agreement was signed [4, p.42].

The League also fought the international opium trade, sexual slavery, and facilitated the position of refugees, especially in Turkey in the period before 1926. One of the innovations of the organization was the introduction in 1922 of the "Nansen Passport" – the first internationally recognized stateless identity card for refugees. According to this document, refugees could move freely in countries that recognized its validity (more than 50 states). It was developed by the League of Nations Commissioner for Refugees, Fritjof Nansen [8, p.13].

So, in the period 1919-1929, the League of Nations settled 30 interstate disputes, which hypothetically could turn into armed conflicts [7, p. 22]. In addition to these successes, the League of Nations also suffered serious failures. The most significant difficulties in the organization's foreign policy were caused by the following conflicts: The Chaco War between Bolivia and Paraguay, 1932-1935; the capture of Manchuria by the Japanese Empire in 1931-1933. The capture of Manchuria was one of the main failures of the League and caused the exclusion of Japan from the organization [4, p.43].

The leading states of the League of Nations, Great Britain and France, chose the strategy of maintaining good neighborly relations with Italy, which allowed the Italian dictator Benito Mussolini to seize Ethiopia in 1935-1936. The League of Nations imposed a ban on the supply of military materials and weapons to Italy. However, due to the non-inclusion of oil in the list, such measures of the League could not stop the war. Ethiopia, Eritrea and Italian Somalia were combined into Italian East Africa.

On July 17, 1936, the civil war began in Spain between the Spanish republicans and nationalists. However, the League was unable to prevent foreign intervention in the conflict. Italy and Germany came to the aid of the Francoists (nationalists), the Soviet Union supported the Spanish republicans [4, p.43].

Researchers agree that precisely the imperfection of the Versailles-Washington system, which formed the basis of the League of Nations, did not contribute to the establishment of world stability. The victorious countries of the First World War (Great Britain, France, the USA and Japan) solved international problems with the maximum benefit for themselves, ignoring the interests of the defeated and recently formed countries [1, p.206].

Despite its failures, the experience of the League of Nations, was valuable for the creation of the United Nations. This organization actually tested the mechanisms of international interaction that formed the basis of the UN. Many UN bodies were either extensions of the League's committees or inspired by them. It is important to note that the UN successfully solved many of the shortcomings in the decision-making and control mechanisms of the League of Nations. The experience of the League also showed how important consensus among the great powers is to ensure lasting peace.

Thus, the first attempt to create a global organization to support the peace faced difficulties. The League of Nations, created as a result of the First World War, failed to create effective mechanisms of influence on world players. The Second World War of 1939-1945 became a clear evidence of the inability of the League of Nations to prevent a global conflict.

The idea of creating a new international organization began to take shape during the Second World War. Important milestones on this path were the Atlantic Charter signed by the leaders of the USA and Great Britain in 1941, and the Declaration of the Soviet government at the Inter-Union Conference of the same year. These documents laid the foundations for future cooperation and the principles of peaceful coexistence.

On October 24, 1945, with the ratification of the UN Charter, the organization officially began its activities. 51 states became its founders including Ukraine. Since then, October 24 has been celebrated as United Nations Day, reminding us of the desire for peace and international cooperation.

The organization's peacekeeping activities began in the late 1940s and early 1950s with surveillance operations. UN observers monitored the situation in the region, compiled reports, investigated incidents and inspected military facilities. The collected information allowed the UN Security Council to make informed decisions. The debut of UN peacekeeping activities took place in 1948 with a mission to monitor the ceasefire in Palestine. Despite the complexities of the "Cold War" (confrontation between the USSR and the USA), when collective security mechanisms were effectively frozen, the UN actively used peacekeeping operations to maintain peace and security around the world [11, p.144]. During the "Cold War" era, the exclusive possession of the right of veto by the leading players of world politics violated the principle of equality of UN member states. Applying this right, the world superpowers of the USSR and the USA created their spheres of influence [2, p.15].

With the end of the Cold War, the peacekeeping activities of the UN underwent a transformation. From traditional military operations, the organization moved to a comprehensive approach aimed at ensuring the implementation of peace agreements and creating a sustainable world. The focus of peacekeeping missions was not interstate conflicts, but internal and civil wars. This required expanding the composition of the missions, including both military personnel and specialists in various fields (administrators, observers, sappers, etc.). After the Cold War, the number of peacekeeping operations increased significantly. Since 1948, the UN

has organized 71 missions, 14 of which continue to this day [5, p.425].

The experience of peacekeeping operations shows that success depends on a number of factors, including the size of the territory. Operations in smaller territories such as Kosovo, Haiti, East Timor and the Solomon Islands have a better chance of success. A key condition for the effective deployment of peacekeeping forces is the achievement of a ceasefire and reconciliation of all parties to the conflict. A clear mandate and sufficient resources are necessary to fulfill the assigned tasks [10, p.28].

Despite the positive cases, the UN has had a number of failures. The researchers include the mission in Rwanda during the 1994 genocide, problems related to the settlement of conflicts in Cyprus, Somalia, Syria, Libya and, until 2022, in the southeast of Ukraine. The question of reforming the organization began to be raised more and more often at the beginning of the XXI century.

In the context of Russia's annexation of Crimea and its armed aggression in the east of Ukraine in 2014, the topic of peacekeeping gained special importance for Ukrainian society. The resolution of the UN General Assembly "Territorial integrity of Ukraine", adopted on March 27, 2014, became the first significant response of the organization to the beginning of Russia's armed aggression against Ukraine. However, the permanent representative of Ukraine at the UN, Serhii Kyslytsia, emphasizes that the special rights of the permanent members of the Security Council hinder the reform of the UN. And the lack of reforms increases the risk of repeating the fate of the League of Nations. In these conditions, the most effective instruments of pressure on Russia were not UN resolutions, but political and economic sanctions introduced by Western countries. They made it possible to slow down Russian aggression against Ukraine and forced the Russian Federation to sit down at the negotiating table, in particular, within the framework of the Trilateral Contact Group (Ukraine, the Russian Federation and the OSCE) and the Normandy contact group (Ukraine, the Russian Federation, France and Germany) [6].

From the point of view of Ukrainian diplomats, UN reforms are desirable in the following aspects: an increase in the number of permanent members of the Security Council for a fairer representation of the world's regions, as well as a review of the right of veto - its limitation or cancellation [3, p.58]. Ukrainian politicians emphasize that the right of veto of the permanent members of the Security Council limits the capabilities of the UN in solving the most important issues of international security, turning the organization into a "powerless observer" [11, p.143; 12].

The Russian Federation continued the practice of the USSR, using the veto to serve its national interests, in particular with regard to the Russian-Ukrainian conflict (an illegal referendum in the Crimea in 2014 and the creation of an international tribunal regarding the downing of the MH-17 aircraft in 2015) and the Syrian conflict [2, pp. 17-18]. The President of Ukraine V. Zelenskyy repeatedly stated in his speeches at the UN that "the right of veto in the hands of the aggressor"

drove the UN into a dead end, turning it into only "the world's most visible tribune." As a first step towards reforming the UN, Zelenskyy proposed giving the General Assembly the opportunity to override the veto "provided two-thirds of the votes, reflecting the will of the nations from Asia, Africa, Europe, both Americas and the Pacific Ocean region." Among other steps to reform the Organization, Zelenskyy named the expansion of the permanent members of the UN Security Council and the creation of a system for preventing aggression through preventive sanctions [2, p.39-40].

The existing system of international relations, including the UN, turned out to be outdated and ineffective. It is unable to ensure international security and solve global problems. The new world leaders, seeking to maintain their influence, are resisting the reforms of the UN and the creation of a new international system of relations.

If the UN cannot adapt to the realities of today's changing world, it risks repeating the fate of the League of Nations and disappearing. The United Nations was created in very different circumstances, when the world was divided into states that had just survived the Second World War. At that time, the UN was needed as a platform for dialogue between all states of the world, regardless of ideologies, economic and political models, to discuss current problems and find compromises.

Conclusions. The creation of the League of Nations and the UN are key milestones in the history of international organizations and diplomatic relations. The League of Nations was founded after the First World War (1914-1918) as a result of the Paris Peace Conference of 1919, and the United Nations after the Second World War (1939-1945) as a result of the San Francisco Conference of 1945.

The League of Nations was the first attempt to create a universal international organization designed to maintain peace and security in the world. The UN was designed with the experience of the League of Nations in mind, which was reflected in its broader powers, decision-making mechanisms and more effective measures to maintain peace and security. The UN received wide international support, most of the world's states were included in its composition, which strengthened its role and authority. Having analyzed the results of the activities of the organizations, it is possible to come to the conclusion about the continuity of many principles laid down by the League of Nations, which are now implemented in the activities of the UN. When creating a new international structure, it was possible to use the achievements of the League of Nations, which made it possible to increase the effectiveness of the UN. However, the modern peacekeeping activities of the UN are often assessed by many experts as low- or medium-effective. Today's problems, such as aggression, selective application of international law, acutely raise questions about reforming the UN.

To increase efficiency, it is advised to take a number of measures, such as preventive actions: emphasis on preventive measures to prevent conflicts. Experts recommend reviewing the mandates of peacekeeping missions, including the right to use force to ensure protection, not just self-defense. Ukraine, represented by

politicians and diplomats, draws attention to the urgent need to reform the UN Security Council.

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